

**THE REFLECTION OF IMMORALITY CAUSED BY
CONSUMERISM IN *THE WINTER OF OUR DISCONTENT*
BY J. STEINBECK**

Niyozov Jumanazar Farxod o'g'li

Teacher at Uzbekistan State University of World Languages
jumanazarnf@gmail.com

Annotation This paper is devoted to an elaborate analysis of *The Winter of Our Discontent* as a novel that depicts the detrimental effects of capitalism in the Americans' life in terms of consumerism and conformism. Through the images and portraits he created for *The Winter of Our Discontent*, Steinbeck described a changing world where the common people were caught in a precarious situation, and unfortunately, they were being sacrificed for the sake of progress. Steinbeck was familiar with the economic forces that affected people's lives. He comprehended them both from the need to make his country economically strong but also from the personal side as people's morality suffered as the victims of capitalism.

Key words: consumerism, conformism, commodity, consumer culture, American Dream, instinctive immorality

Introduction

In the last years of his life, Steinbeck published biting analyses of America, non-fiction works like *Travels with Charley in Search of America* (1962) and *America and Americans* (1966). These works reveal the author's view of the dramatic decline of American culture and the immorality of the American condition. The series of non-fiction essays entitled *America and Americans* offers cynical commentary

on the state of the union such as, "Why are we on this verge of moral and hence nervous collapse? [...] I believe it is because we have reached the end of a road and have no new path to take, no duty to carry out, and no purpose to fulfill" [4, p.397]. This sense of nihilism suffuses *The Winter of Our Discontent* as well, where Steinbeck blames a large part of this "moral collapse" on capitalism and the overwhelming presence of consumerism. In his

estimation, the absence of morality comes along with these developments. Through the portrayal of the moral fall of Ethan Hawley, Steinbeck suggests the bleak future of America, yet the conclusion of the novel hints at a sense of possibility for future generations.

Materials and Methodology

We implemented historical approach to study the history of the American society when the novel set in detail in order to investigate and find out the historical factors that influenced the nation's psychology. We utilised the psychological approach as well to search for the motives that compel characters to act in a certain way. Two main works in the field of philosophy are utilized in order to illustrate the appearance and development of conformism in society's mentality. These are *The Consumer Society: Myths and Structures* by Baudrillard, Jean and *Society and the Spectacle* by Debord, Guy.

In the epigraph to *The Winter of Our Discontent*, Steinbeck offers this disclaimer: "Readers seeking to identify the fictional people and places here described would do better to inspect

their own communities and search their own hearts, for this book is about a large part of America today" [5, p.1]. This book is about debatable morality, lustrous temptresses, an insatiable appetite for fortune, commodification of goods, and unyielding materialism. Steinbeck warns readers to look to their own communities to witness the devastation of capitalism, the greed of our fathers, and the dissatisfaction that plagues great success. Steinbeck's final novel reveals the cynical tone of an author who has dissected America and Americans for his entire literary career.

Results and Discussion

As Steinbeck's final piece of fiction, *The Winter of Our Discontent* represents the culmination of his trenchant attacks against typical American ideals such as marriage, the domesticity of women, disillusionment and male-centred business. The culmination of these criticisms manifests in this text in which Steinbeck holds nothing back. The evils of capitalism surface through the juxtaposition of nature versus modernity, the family pressures acting on Ethan to attain a higher economic

status, and the compulsory happiness perpetrated by dominant capitalist ideology. Notably, Baudrillard's *The Consumer Society* (1970) provides a useful theoretical backdrop for understanding Steinbeck's critical approach to society in *The Winter of Our Discontent*.

When paired with Baudrillard's critical discussion of capitalism, Steinbeck's texts, both fiction and non-fiction, further explain the consumerist tendencies of modern Americans and document the prevalence of consumerism in American culture. Baudrillard affirms,

In the phenomenology of consumption, this general 'air-conditioning' of life, goods, objects, services, behavior and social relations represents the perfected, 'consummated' stage of an evolution which runs from affluence pure and simple, through interconnected networks of objects, to the total conditioning of action and time, and finally to the systematic atmospherics built into those cities of the future [1, p.29].

Here, Baudrillard unfolds a comprehensive explanation of consumerism and the future of modern cities. Baudrillard cites the "air-conditioning" quality of modern environments, implying the manufactured quality of everything that exists in modern culture; this synthetic environment suggests the constructed, disposable attributes of all facets of life in a consumer society. The phenomenon of consumerism can be seen in the proliferation of "goods, objects, services, behaviour and social relations" which generally encompasses everything the modern individual encounters daily. In addition, Steinbeck incorporates the illusion of the American Dream as a central theme to his works and continues this theme in *The Winter of Our Discontent*. The character of Ethan faces the moral complexities of modernism and as Baudrillard suggests, Ethan must conform to the "air-conditioning" quality, the illusory element of modern culture. Through Ethan's fall from morality in his attempt to attain financial success, Steinbeck unveils the elusive nature of the American Dream.

What Baudrillard calls the importance and “celebration of the object” is clearly communicated in *The Winter of Our Discontent*. In *The Consumer Society*, Baudrillard comments on the prevalence of these objects: “*the humans of the age of affluence are surrounded not so much by other human beings, as they were in previous ages, but by objects. Their daily dealings are now not so much with their fellow men, but rather—on a rising statistical curve—with the reception and manipulation of goods and messages*” [1, p.25]. Baudrillard compares human beings with receptors for goods and messages, as life is now cluttered with the sending and receiving of information and the purchasing of goods. The sanctity of the commodity has materialized as the primary sacrament for modern humans living in the “age of affluence” and can be seen through insistent globalization and construction of new industry designed for the “manipulation of goods and messages.” Later in the text, Baudrillard suggests, “*Happiness has to be measurable. It has to be a well-being measurable in terms of objects and*

signs; it has to be ‘comfort’” [1, p.49]. Here, the comfort of the American individual depends upon happiness calculated in measurable terms, not only by objects themselves, but by the cultural signification of these objects.

In the formula for social success in America, the accumulation of objects equals calculable wealth, comfort, happiness, yet what exactly do these concepts signify? In the context of modern culture, these objects instil a sense of power in their owner, a feeling of accomplishment and comfort sought by their consumers. Even Steinbeck discusses the American dependency on the object: “*We are also poisoned with things. Having many things seems to create a desire for more things, more clothes, houses, automobiles [...] We are trapped and entangled in things*” [4, p.396]. The capitalist state is responsible for this entanglement in things and the perpetuation of the commodity. In *Society of the Spectacle*, Guy Debord identifies the importance of the commodity as a critical feature of capitalist social organization, “*The commodity appears in fact as a power which comes to occupy social life. It is*

then that the political economy takes shape, as the dominant science and the science of domination. The spectacle is the moment when the commodity has attained the total occupation of social life” [3, pp.41-42]. Debord’s argument scrutinizes modern culture by demonstrating how society idolizes the commodity and allows it to completely commandeer social life. Postmodern Marxists like Baudrillard and Debord examine the omnipresence of the commodity in consumer culture and interpret the power of the commodity as a main contributor to spectacular society.

In *The Winter of Our Discontent*, the character of Ethan Hawley and the city of New Baytown embody these criticisms regarding consumer culture. Steinbeck highlights the infestation of modernization through the contrast between natural imagery and the heavy hand of machinery. Steinbeck begins,

[Ethan and Joey Morphy] had come to the corner where Elm angles into High Street. Automatically they stopped and turned to look at the pink brick and plaster mess that was the old Bay Hotel, now being wrecked to make

room for the new Woolworth’s. The yellow-painted bulldozer and the big crane that swung the wrecking ball were silent like waiting predators in the early morning [5, p.9].

Here, Steinbeck flexes his cynicism and illustrates the perfect pairing of contemporary mechanics with natural images to underscore the loss of nature and old-world antiquity with the influx of machinery.

The image of the “crane” initially establishes the juxtaposition between the natural environment and the construction site portrayed in this scene. The “crane” marks the shift from the natural environment to the mechanical invasion of America, particularly through the destruction of nature due to trends like urbanization and the construction of consumerist locations. Steinbeck mentions the “yellow-painted bulldozer,” “the big crane,” and “the wrecking ball” as landmarks in the future of America; its push toward consumerism will bring more scenes like this and eventually destroy America’s original history, symbolized by the old Bay Hotel. The images of destruction suggest an all-

encompassing moral apocalypse and the elimination of the American historical setting due to extreme urbanization. Through the contrast of nature versus machinery, Steinbeck stresses the “yellow-painted” machine, highlighting the fact that it is painted yellow and does not exist naturally. The frigid images of the machine contrast the earthly connotation of “silent like waiting predators in the early morning.” Using the conflict between predator and prey, Steinbeck creates the inevitable consumption of nature by capitalism (predator) and the destruction of nature and historical antiquity (prey).

Early in *The Winter of Our Discontent*, Steinbeck introduces the “mourning” of the loss of antiquity and displays the view of local history as “old” and ridicules the importance of modernism (the “new Woolworth’s”). Ethan and Joey “automatically” stop to revel in the destruction of their antique town and shame the advent of new drug stores. The Bay Hotel exemplifies the obliteration of historic locality in America (a “pink brick and plaster mess”) and faces destruction to “make room” for the bright neon lights of

capitalism. As suggested by Baudrillard, daily life consists of less contact with fellow men and more interaction with goods. The construction site interrupts their conversation and predicts the decline of human interaction due to consumerism and the commodity. The Woolworth’s will house a surplus of commodities for sale and demonstrates the need for measurable wealth in terms of goods as social signifiers. Evident by the construction of Woolworth’s, Steinbeck conveys the rise of this phenomenon happening throughout America, even in unspoiled fishing villages like New Baytown. Steinbeck’s own theories about America explain this incessant need for modernity in terms of social strata: “*the top people have the newest models, and lesser folk buy the used homes turned in as down payments on the newer ones*” [4, p.334]. Like the Bay Hotel, tired goods are exchanged for the newer, shinier ones and give their owners an accomplished feeling of social mobility. The desperate need for social mobility floods the novel and represents a main motivator for Ethan’s moral questioning.

As Steinbeck affirms in the epigraph of *The Winter of Our Discontent*, the moral devastation of New Baytown represent a microcosm, a fictional morsel of the real dilemmas facing America as a capitalist nation. The text annihilates the deceptive illusion of the American Dream and devalues the precious myth of American prosperity, a dangerous myth generally devoid of any reality. A destructive fascination with the American Dream also occurs in *The Winter of Our Discontent* through Ethan. Steinbeck implements a single image, a manifestation of all the reminders for the cultural myth of boundless prosperity to be discovered and seized in the illusion of the American Dream.

In the text *The Way We Never Were: American Families and the Nostalgia Trap* (2000), Stephanie Coontz focuses on the façade of the American family and the consumerist rise that followed the predominance of the nuclear family in the 1950s:

The 1950s was a profamily period if there ever was one. Rates of divorce and illegitimacy were half of what they are today; marriage was almost

universally praised; the family was everywhere hailed as the most basic institution in society [...] For most Americans, the most salient symbol and immediate beneficiary of their newfound prosperity was the nuclear family. The biggest boom in consumer spending, for example, was in household goods [2, pp.24-25]

The 1950s are commonly referred to as the era of the “nuclear family” and as displayed in Coontz’s argument, the revival of family as the “most basic institution in society.” The nuclear family and the concentration on household goods propelled consumer spending to incredible heights. Due to the prosperity of Americans in the 1950s, the family could now enjoy household luxuries (television, refrigerator, car) and families experienced the social pressure to acquire these goods as a quantifiable measurement of social placement. The 1950s also saw a rise in the “middle class” and therefore, an accompanying pressure to obtain this social status.

In *The Winter of Our Discontent*, Ethan Hawley experiences this intense pressure to acquire wealth and

eventually brings great shame to the family due to his immoral means of attaining it. The Hawley family looks to Ethan to provide them with the middle class niceties enjoyed by other Americans. In order to demonstrate this pressure early in the text, Steinbeck opens the novel with the following lines: “When the fair gold morning of April stirred Mary Hawley awake, she turned over to her husband and saw him, little fingers pulling a frog mouth at her” [5, p.3]. The opening lines of *The Winter of Our Discontent* display Ethan’s playfulness towards his loyal, honest wife. A playfulness Mary sees as his silly antics. A playfulness Ethan utilizes to hide his anxieties from his wife. A playfulness masking the troubles that haunt Ethan and keep him lurking the streets of New Baytown in the dead of night. Steinbeck portrays Ethan’s teasing to emphasize the angst buried deep within his psyche and ironically, Ethan plays these games with his wife in order to conceal the anxiety she instils in him. Even the immediate inclusion of the “gold morning” that awakens Mary suggests that this is the thing that moves her. Mary and the children create an

image of the typical American domestic setting and expect Ethan to provide it for them.

Due to Ethan’s inability to obtain their desired fortune, this produces a sense of lacking within him and propels him to consider immoral means to satisfy their every wish, especially Mary’s. Ethan ponders, “*The structure of my change was feeling, pressures from without, Mary’s wish, Allen’s desires, Ellen’s anger, Mr. Baker’s help [...] Suppose my humble and interminable clerkship was not virtue at all but a moral laziness? For any success, boldness is required*” [5, p.91]. This moment marks the beginning of Ethan’s justification for his immoral decisions and suggests that pressures “from without” drive Ethan to relinquish his “built-in judge.” Ethan carries the weight of his family’s economic inadequacy and begins blaming his monotonous, incessant clerkship as the root of his problems.

Baudrillard states, “*a society achieves equilibrium not through its virtues but through its vices, and that social peace, progress and human happiness are obtained by the*

instinctive immorality which leads them to continually break the rules” [1, p.42]. Here, Baudrillard’s idea of “instinctive immorality” perfectly explains Ethan’s compulsion for boldness and illustrates his plans to shed his role as the lowly grocery clerk. In *America and Americans*, Steinbeck continues this idea of instinctive immorality, “*We scramble and scabble up the stony path toward the pot of gold we have taken to mean security. We trample friends, relatives, and strangers who get in our way of achieving it*” [4, p.330]. Steinbeck intentionally utilizes the pronoun “we” to express that “we” as Americans are all guilty of this immoral decadence and Steinbeck displays its implications through Ethan’s fall from morality.

In hopes of satisfying Mary’s middle-class desires, Ethan performs a kaleidoscope of deceitful, conniving acts against those closest to him. Primarily, Ethan discovers Marullo (the grocery store owner) has been living in America illegally and decides to turn in the suspected alien. After Ethan reports Marullo to the federal government, Marullo is deported to Sicily and has no

choice but to give Ethan ownership of the store. When Mary learns that Ethan now owns the grocery, they share the following exchange:

‘You mean—you mean you own the store?’

‘Yes.’

‘You’re not a clerk! Not a clerk!’

She rolled face down in the pillows and wept, big, full-bosomed sobs, the way a slave might when the collar is struck off [5, p.238].

Here, Steinbeck emphasizes Mary’s incredible shame in the community and now, like a slave freed from the shackles of poverty, Mary can hold her head up. The humiliation of inadequate wealth holds Mary by the throat, tightly choking her neck and preventing her from enjoying the privileges of a bourgeois lifestyle. The repetition of “not a clerk!” validates Mary’s embarrassment as the grocer’s wife and Steinbeck comments on the taut chokehold of capitalism.

The comparison of Mary to a freed slave introduces the role of women, particularly housewives, as contributors to the rise of consumerism. Returning to *The Consumer Society*, Baudrillard

discusses the role of women in terms of advertising in a consumerist culture,

Woman, whose fate lies with the paraphernalia (household objects), fulfills not only an economic function, but a prestige function, deriving from the aristocratic or bourgeois idleness of women [...] the housewife does not produce, she does not show up in the nation's accounts; she is not recorded as a productive force. She is, in fact, fated to be of value as a force of prestige, by her official uselessness, by her status as a 'kept' slave. [1, p.97].

Baudrillard's quote regarding the feminine paradigm, in which the cultural ideal of "woman is sold to women," distinctly relates to Mary's fuss over household goods, a proper wardrobe for the children and her overwhelming happiness for Ethan's change in status.

Once Mary's manacles of inadequacy have been removed, she can fully actualize her role as the image of the idle wife in the bourgeois home. The position of the housewife fulfils a certain economic function. Due to her idle, leisure time, Mary serves as the consumer of "household objects" kept

as a slave to her domestic function to further breed the consumerist cycle. As Ethan "takes stock" of all the pressures acting against him, he describes Mary's wishes: "By money, Mary meant new curtains and sure education for the kids and holding her head a little higher and, face it, being proud rather than a little ashamed of me" [5, p.45]. Mary subscribes to the cultural model of femininity and domesticity, fulfilling Baudrillard's idea regarding the "prestige function" of the housewife role and expecting her husband to satisfy her petty fondness for the paraphernalia of modern life. The family unit serves as an entity to reinforce certain dominant values accepted by mainstream culture. Following this idea, Mary exhibits immense concern for the Hawley's status in New Baytown and fuels Ethan's obsession with obtaining a great fortune for her own satisfaction. The Hawley family's desire for materials and increased wealth represent the main contributing factor to Ethan's moral degradation, evident by his depraved efforts to provide for their unnecessary

desires, although considered vital by American consumerist standards.

Ethan learns the first rule of Joey Morphy's "Guide to Business Prosperity", "money gets money." Ethan unlocks the store and proclaims his opening sermon to the waiting congregation of groceries:

If the laws of thinking are the laws of things, then morals are relative too, and manner and sin—that's relative too in a relative universe. Has to be. No getting away from it. Point of reference. You dry cereal with the Mickey Mouse mask on the box and a ventriloquism gadget for the label and ten cents. I'll have to take you home, but right now you sit up and listen [5, p.57].

After receiving Joey Morphy's advice, Ethan begins to understand the moral blindness necessary for success in America. The Mickey Mouse mask represents a false identity for Ethan. The mouse mask embodies the commodity, the consumer need for it and, if he follows The Morph's advice, Ethan must first acquire money in order to make more, likely through dishonest means.

Steinbeck introduces the theme of "ventriloquism" through the image of the Mickey Mouse mask and this theme details Ethan's inability to utilize his own free will. Steinbeck suggests Ethan is merely a talking puppet and his puppeteer, capitalism, determines his every move, his every thought. Here, Ethan is nothing less than a slave to the system and acts as a cog in the capitalist machine. Ethan abandons his freedom of choice and transforms into a functioning member of the system. Feelings of economic inadequacy and immoral motivations explain Ethan's assimilation into predominant consumerist thought. The early appearance of Mickey Mouse establishes Ethan's exploration of dishonest, conniving methods implemented by countless others who have reached economic success and here, Ethan attempts to validate their lack of virtue by proposing that business ethics and morality and sin are all relative, possibly even worthy of forgiveness. Although Ethan has not committed any immoral act yet, the Mickey Mouse motif follows Ethan at each pivotal moment in his ethical

deterioration. Moreover, the material desires of his wife and children deplete Ethan's moral register, evident by his participation in consumer culture. Ethan says to the Mickey Mouse cereal, "I'll have to take you home, but right now you sit up and listen" [5, p.89]. Through this comment, Ethan implies how Mickey Mouse, the symbol for capitalism, does most of the talking and the fact that Ethan must take it home confirms Mary and the children embody the root of Ethan's consumerist motivations.

Conclusion

Ethan's rationalization for his moral corruption derives from external pressures and the "thousand moral rules" broken for the sake of maintaining the status quo, as Baudrillard proposes, citizens are plagued with "instinctive immorality" in order to maintain social equilibrium. Ethan embodies this compulsory action for immorality, as success is only achieved through "boldness" and virtue is essentially insignificant. Ethan allows the illusion of "security" to take the wheel and betray his friends (Marullo)

and relatives (Danny) to acquire the fortune Mary so desperately desires, as outlined in Steinbeck's idea from *America and Americans*. Ethan acknowledges his change in moral values by confessing "the structure of [his] change," insinuating the low value of moral responsibility when it comes to attain wealth in America.

In the last chapter of Part One, Steinbeck cites the inspiration for the title and quotes Shakespeare's Richard III, "Now is the winter of our discontent/Made glorious by this sun of York" [5, p.157]. In this chapter, Steinbeck uses the word "discontent" three times in order to illustrate Ethan's deplorable transformation to amoral monster as he learns the nature of true discontent. The epigraph states, "this book is about a large part of America today" and Steinbeck includes the collective "we" and "us" as victims of this consumerist takeover. Notably, Steinbeck hints at the winter of "our" discontent, demonstrating the discontent all Americans experience in light of the pressure that capitalism places upon society.

References

1. Baudrillard, Jean. *The Consumer Society: Myths and Structures*. Trans. Chris Turner. London: Sage Publications, 1970.
2. Coontz, Stephanie. *The Way We Never Were: American Families and the Nostalgia Trap*, University of Missouri Press, 2000.
3. Debord, Guy. *Society of the Spectacle*. Detroit: Black & Red, 1970.
4. Steinbeck, John. *America and Americans and Selected Nonfiction*. 2002 ed. New York: Penguin Books.
5. Steinbeck, John. *The Winter of Our Discontent*. New York: Penguin Books, 1961.
6. Timmerman, John H. *John Steinbeck's Fiction: The Aesthetics of the Road Taken*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 2006.
7. Weeks, Edward. "Review: *The Winter of Our Discontent*, by John Steinbeck". *Atlantic Monthly*. Retrieved 2011-08-08.